

THE CONCEPT OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCE BASED ON ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCES

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Abstract: Identifying strategies and concepts for improving the quality of teacher training in the new socio-cultural reality increases the need for research of a theoretical and methodological nature, in which the adoption of innovative pedagogical experience is considered as a mechanism for future teacher training. The ability to develop innovations in the conditions of innovative renewal of all areas of society, complexity and development of the dynamics of the labor market and the market of educational services related to it is evidence of the specialist's education, his readiness to perform professional functions. In this thesis, based on foreign experiences, scientific analytical thoughts on the conception of future pedagogues on the development of innovative pedagogic experience are presented.

Key words: professional training, innovative pedagogical experience, concept, model, organizational and pedagogical conditions.

Introduction:

In a dynamically changing world, the development of society directly depends on the training of a new type of teacher who has the ability to innovatively change the pedagogical reality, master the accumulated innovative experience. A teacher who is able to highlight current problems and identify innovative methods and tools for solving them becomes the main source of modern education. In the higher education system, ensuring the requirements for the qualifications of graduates is emphasized as an important direction, expanding the scope of innovative activities of educational subjects, strengthening incentives for continuous innovative activities, and developing innovations it is emphasized that it is necessary to create a favorable environment for.

The need to prepare future teachers for the development of pedagogical innovations is not only a social demand, but also related to the needs of general secondary education institutions that need creative teachers. The need to acquire innovative experience is also manifested in the future teachers themselves, it is necessary for them to participate in scientific conferences, seminars and innovative pedagogical experience, master classes of successful teachers of the republic, development and protection of innovative projects is confirmed by active participation in other forms of information exchange [1, 95-b]. The social order formed at all levels to prepare the teacher for the development of innovative pedagogical experience makes the search for effective approaches to its satisfaction by higher education institutions and, first of all, higher pedagogical education institutions. Our empirical research has shown that more than 60% of future teachers need help in systematizing knowledge about the nature of innovative pedagogical experience and its manifestation. Attaching a number of schools to pedagogical universities, foreign experience in

implementing the ideas of advanced pedagogical experience in the professional training of teachers, modern experience of transforming pedagogical universities into an educational, scientific and innovative complex, with general educational institutions of republican universities strengthening integration.

In previous studies in pedagogy and psychology, the preparation of university students to learn pedagogical experience is reduced to its individual stages, the teacher's idea of innovative pedagogical experience is mainly formed at the stage of professional development. Available diagnostic tools are also designed for this. However, modern trends require a different approach to the training of future teachers, which is dominated by the development of pedagogical innovations, the creation of new innovative products, and the enrichment of each future teacher's own pedagogical experience.

Literature Review The idea that future teachers need to be specifically trained to develop innovative pedagogical practices is not new. Judgments about the impact of pedagogical experience on the development of educational theory and practice can be found in the works of I. F. Herbart, N. I. Pirogov, L. N. Tolstoy, K. D. Ushinsky, and others. Well-known teachers P. P. Blonsky, A. S. Makarenko, M. M. Pist, V. A. Sukhomlinsky and others consider the preparation of the teacher for the study of pedagogical experience [3, p. 145].

Methodology and methods.

The theoretical and methodological foundations of preparing future teachers for the development of innovative pedagogical experience are as follows:

- genesis of future teacher training;
- socio-cultural trends that determine the specific characteristics of the historical development of training;
- basic principles of philosophical-anthropological, synergetic, praxeological, environmental and competence-based approaches.

The genesis of the training of future teachers is based on the requirements for the development of education in different historical periods (from meeting society's need for qualified personnel to creating an environment for the formation of a new type of teacher with practical and transformational competence) is revealed by phase separation.

Analyzing trends in the development of teacher's professional training in general and preparation for mastering innovative pedagogical experience in particular. made it possible to consider preparation for mastering. The leading ideas of these approaches are aimed at considering the preparation of future teachers for the development of innovative pedagogical experience as a way of organizing the educational process in which the important forces of the future teacher are renewed and formed as a person in all his integrity. The main rules of the current approaches are aimed at creating conditions for future teachers to strive to change the surrounding reality, to reach new levels of personal and professional self-development, value attitude to pedagogical innovations and pedagogical forecasting skills [4, 61 -b].

Research results.

The study showed that using the educational potential of innovative pedagogical experience in the training of future teachers supports the current state of practical training and implements a strategy for its development. This strategy opens the features for the formation of the innovative personality of the future teacher, his self-awareness, self-development. Methodological directions of teaching at the methodological level, the essence of innovative pedagogical experience is the search, formation and development of radically

new educational and educational doctrines, concepts, paradigms of the pedagogical team (teacher) that have been normatively approved by the scientific community and the pedagogical community is defined as the result of innovative activities on development, which ensures long-term, stable success in their consistent and complete implementation.

The criteria for evaluating the preparation of future teachers for the development of innovative pedagogical experience are reduced to the components of preparation:

- personal (thinking, motives, personality traits);
- cognitive (knowledge);
- operational (skills).

At the practical level, the organizational and pedagogical conditions for preparing future teachers for the development of innovative pedagogical experience are described:

- comprehensive use of the main resources of the innovative educational environment;
- scientific methodological support;
- diagnostic support for the professional formation of future teachers [2, p. 23].

The integrated use of the main resources of the innovative educational environment includes the compliance of the blocks of the innovative educational environment (*infrastructure, technological and pedagogical support*) with the predictive model components, the use of the resources of the innovative educational environment at all stages of preparation implementation of the main directions of activity on the implementation of a complex of educational technologies and methods.

Conclusion:

In general, the volume of knowledge about innovative pedagogical experience and the level of formation of skills to master it constitutes the pedagogical experience of future teachers. It determines the effectiveness and intensity of innovation. Thus, the sufficiently high level of knowledge of future teachers about innovative pedagogical experience and the level of formation of their professional and creative competences, determined during the internal monitoring process, confirms the need for special training of teachers for the development of innovative pedagogical experience

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